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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF IMMEDIATE
RELEASE TABLETS OF CLOBAZAM BY USING WET
GRANULATION METHOD**Aukunuru Jithan^{1,2}, Sravani Marripalli¹¹Department of Pharmaceutics, Omega College Of Pharmacy, Osmania university, Telangana, India²Technology Consultants, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.**Article Received: August 2024 Accepted: September 2024 Published: October 2024****Abstract:**

An Orally disintegrating tablet disperses readily in saliva and the drug is available in solution or suspension form for the immediate absorption and resulting in rapid onset of action. In the present research work Clobazam Orally disintegrating tablet were prepared by intra and extra granulation technique method using varying concentrations of Fenugreek Gum, Karaya Gum and Crospovidone super disintegrants. The formulations prepared were evaluated for precompression & post compression parameters. From the drug excipient compatibility studies we observe that there are no interactions between the pure drug (Clobazam) and optimized formulation (Clobazam + excipients) which indicates there are no physical changes. Post compression parameters was found to be within the limits. Among the formulation prepared the tablet containing concentration of Crospovidone shows 99.72% of the drug release within 60 min & follows first order kinetics. The overall result indicated that the formulation F12 containing Crospovidone is better and fulfilling of the needs of the Orally disintegrating tablet.

Crucial words: Orally disintegrating tablet, Clobazam, Crospovidone, FTIR.**Corresponding author:****Sravani Marripalli,**Department of Pharmaceutics, Omega College Of Pharmacy,
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INTRODUCTION:

An ideal dosage regimen in the drug therapy of any disease is the one which immediately attains the desired therapeutic concentration of drug in plasma (or at the site of action) and maintains it constant for entire duration of treatment. This is possible through administration of conventional dosage form in a particular dose at a particular frequency. Thus drug may administered by variety routes in variety of dosage form¹. Oral route is most common and popular route of administration of drug is oral route because of its systemic effect, patient compliance, less expensive to manufacture. Tablet provides high precision dosing. Tablet form is the most widely used dosage form because of self-administration and ease in manufacturing. In most of the cases immediate on set of action is required as compare to conventional therapy. To achieve the rapid onset of action and eliminate the drawbacks of conventional therapy immediate release dosage form is now a days popular and used as an alternative oral dosage form. Immediate release tablet are very quickly after administration.

Immediate Release Dosage Form:

Immediate release tablets are designed to disintegrate and release the drug in absence of any controlling features such as coating or other formulation techniques⁵. The solution containing the active ingredients is swallowed, and the active ingredients are then absorbed through the gastrointestinal epithelium to reach the target and produce the desired effect⁶

Advantages of Tablets:

- They are unit dosage form, and they offer the capabilities of all oral dosage forms for the dose precision and the least content variability during dosing.
- Accuracy and uniformity of drug content.
- Optimal drug dissolution and hence, availability from the dosage form for absorption consistent with intended use (i.e., immediate or extended release).
- Usually taken orally, but can be administered sublingually, rectally or intra-vaginally.
- Their cost is lowest of all oral dosage form.
- They are the most compact of all oral dosage forms.
- They are in general the easier and cheaper to package and ship as compare to other oral dosage forms.
- Product identification is simple and cheap, requiring no additional processing steps when employing an embossed or monogrammed punch face.

- They are ease to administer, does not require a specialist.
- They are better suited to large-scale production than other unit oral forms.
- They have the better properties of chemical, mechanical and microbiological stability.
- Easy to prepare.
- Provide prolonged stability to medicaments.
- Formulate as a special release products such as enteric or delayed release products.
- Easy to divide into halves and quarters whenever fraction dose is required
- Improved compliance/added convenience
- Improved stability, bioavailability
- Suitable for controlled/sustained release actives
- Allows high drug loading
- Ability to provide advantages of liquid medication in the form of solid preparation.
- Adaptable and amenable to existing processing and packaging machinery
- Cost- effective
- Improved solubility of the pharmaceutical composition
- Decreased disintegration and dissolution times for immediate release oral dosage forms.

Polymers Used:**Bulking Agents:**

Bulking agents are significant in the formulation of fast-melting tablets. The material contributes functions of a diluents, filler and cost reducer. Bulking agents improve the textural characteristics that in turn enhance the disintegration in the mouth, besides; adding bulk also reduces the concentration of the active in the composition. The recommended bulking agents for this delivery system should be more sugar-based such as mannitol, polydextrose, lactitol, DCL (direct compressible lactose) and starch hydrolystate for higher aqueous solubility and good sensory perception. Mannitol in particular has high aqueous solubility and good sensory perception. Bulking agents are added in the range of 10 percent to about 90 percent by weight of the final composition.

Lubricants:

Lubricants, though not essential excipients, can further assist in making these tablets more palatable after they disintegrate in the mouth. Lubricants remove grittiness and assist in the drug transport mechanism from the mouth down into the stomach.

Carrier Materials:

For therapeutic purposes, the pharmaceutical compositions of the present invention comprise micronized drug in a desired amount in combination with one or more pharmaceutically-acceptable carrier materials appropriate to the indicated route of administration. Oral dosage forms of the pharmaceutical compositions of the present invention preferably comprise micronized drug in a desired amount admixed with one or more carrier materials selected from the group consisting of diluents, disintegrants, binding agents and adhesives, wetting agents, lubricants, anti-adherent agents and/or other carrier materials. More preferably, such compositions are tableted or encapsulated for convenient administration. Such capsules or tablets can be in the form of immediate release capsules or tablets, or can contain a controlled-release formulation as can be provided. For example, in a dispersion of drug in hydroxypropyl methylcellulose. Injectable dosage forms preferably are adapted for parenteral injection. Preferably, these dosage forms comprise micronized drug in aqueous or non-aqueous isotonic sterile injection solutions or suspensions, such as drug suspended or dissolved in water, polyethylene glycol, propylene glycol, ethanol, corn oil, cottonseed oil, peanut oil, sesame oil, benzyl alcohol, sodium chloride, and/or various buffers. These solutions and suspensions can be prepared from sterile powders or granules having one or more of the carriers or diluents mentioned for use in the formulations for oral administration.

Super Disintegrants [7]:

A disintegrant is an excipient, which is added to a tablet or capsule blend to aid in the breakup of the compacted mass when it is put into a fluid environment. Pharmaceutical products designed for oral delivery and currently available on the prescription and over-the-counter markets are mostly the immediate release type, which are designed for immediate release of drug for rapid absorption. Disintegrating agents are substances routinely included in tablet formulations and in some hard shell capsule formulations to promote moisture penetration and dispersion of the matrix of the dosage form in dissolution fluids. Superdisintegrant improve disintegrant efficiency resulting in decreased use levels when compared to traditional disintegrants. Traditionally, starch has been the disintegrant of choice in tablet formulation, and it is still widely used. For instance, starch generally has to be present at levels greater than 5% to adversely affect compatibility, especially in direct compression. Drug

release from a solid dosage form can be enhanced by addition of suitable disintegrants.

Mechanism of Disintegrants:

- 1) High swellability
- 2) Capillary action and high swellability
- 3) Chemical reaction

When introduced to an aqueous environment of use, the tablet rapidly takes up water, leading to swelling of the disintegrant and rapid disintegration of the tablet before the dispersion polymer can form a hydrogel. The disintegrant should be chosen such that it:

- (1) Swells rapidly when introduced into the use environment
- (2) Has a low tendency to form or promote formation of a hydrogel.

W=PAV**Where,**

- W is the work or swelling energy of the disintegrant,
- P is the pressure applied by the probe,
- ΔV is the volume change of the sample.

Advantages:

1. Effective in lower concentrations
2. Less effect on compressibility and flow ability
3. More effective intragranularly some super disintegrants are:

Surfactants:

One very useful class of excipients is surfactants, preferably present from 0 to 10 wt %. Suitable surfactants include fatty acid and alkyl sulfonates; commercial surfactants such as benzalkonium chloride, dioctyl sodium sulfosuccinate, poly oxy ethylene sorbitan fatty acid esters, natural surfactants such as sodium taurocholic acid, lecithin, and other phospholipids and mono- and diglycerides; and mixtures thereof. Such materials can advantageously be employed to increase the rate of dissolution by, for example, facilitating wetting, or otherwise increase the rate of drug release from the dosage form.

pH Modifiers:

Inclusion of pH modifiers such as acids, bases, or buffers may also be beneficial in an amount of from 0 to 10 wt %. Acidic pH modifiers (e.g., acids such as citric acid or succinic acid) retard the dissolution of the pharmaceutical composition when the dispersion polymer is anionic. Alternatively, basic pH modifiers (e.g., sodium acetate or amines) enhance the rate of dissolution of the same types of pharmaceutical composition.

Other Excipients:

Excipients balance the properties of the actives in immediate release dosage forms. This demands a thorough understanding of the chemistry of these excipients to prevent interaction with the actives. Determining the cost of these ingredients is another issue that needs to be addressed by formulators. The role of excipients is important in the formulation of fast-melting tablets. These inactive food grade ingredients, when incorporated in the formulation, impart the desired organoleptic properties and product efficacy. Excipients are general and can be used for a broad range of actives, except some actives that require masking agents [10].

Technique Used in the Preparation of Immediate Release Tablets [11]:

- Tablet molding technique
- Granulation technique
- Direct compression technique
- Mass extrusion technique Tablet Molding

Tablet molding technique:

In this technology, water-soluble ingredients are used so that tablet disintegrate and dissolve rapidly. The powder blend is moistened with a hydro alcoholic solvent and is molded into tablet using compression pressure lower than used in conventional tablets compression. The solvent is then removed by air-drying. Molded tablets have a porous structure that enhances dissolution. Two problems commonly encountered are mechanical strength and poor taste masking characteristics. Using binding agents such as sucrose, acacia or poly vinyl pyrrolidone can increase the mechanical strength of the tablet. To overcome poor taste masking characteristic Van Scoik incorporated drug containing discrete particles, which were formed by spray congealing a molten mixture of hydrogenated cottonseed oil, sodium bicarbonate, lecithin, polyethylene glycol and active ingredient into a lactose based tablet triturate form.

Mass extrusion technique Tablet Molding [12]:

This technology involves softening the active blend using the solvent mixture of water-soluble polyethylene glycol and methanol and subsequent expulsion of softened mass through the extruder or syringe to get a cylinder of the product into even segments using heated blade to form tablets. The dried cylinder can also be used to coat granules for bitter drugs and thereby achieve taste masking Immediate release solid dosage forms prepared by solid dispersions. When formulating such solid amorphous dispersions into immediate release solid dosage forms for oral administration to a use environment such as

the GI tract of an animal such as a human, it is often desirable to maximize the amount of dispersion present in the dosage form. This minimizes the size of the solid dosage form required to achieve the desired dose.

Direct Compression Method:

In this method, tablets are compressed directly from the mixture of the drug and excipients without any preliminary treatment. The mixture to be compressed must have adequate flow properties and cohere under pressure thus making pretreatment as wet granulation unnecessary. Few drugs can be directly compressed into tablets of acceptable quality. A type of disintegrant and its proportion are of prime importance. The other factors to be considered are particle size distribution, contact angle, pore size distribution, tablet hardness and water absorption capacity. All these factors determine the disintegration. The disintegrant addition technology is cost effective and easy to implement at industrial level.

Advantages:

- Direct compression is more efficient and economical process as compared to other processes, because it involves only dry blending and compaction of API and necessary excipients.
- The most important advantage of direct compression is that it is a less economical process. Reduced processing time, reduced labor costs, fewer manufacturing step, and less number of equipment's are required, less process validation, reduced consumption of power. Elimination of heat and moisture, thus increasing not only the stability but also the suitability of the process for thermolabile and moisture sensitive API.
- Particle size uniformity.
- Prime particle dissolution.
- In case of directly compressed tablets after disintegration, each primary drug particle is liberated. While in the case of tablets prepared by compression of granules, small drug particles with a larger surface area adhere together into larger agglomerates; thus, decreasing the surface area available for dissolution.
- The chances of batch-to-batch variation are negligible, because the unit operations required for manufacturing processes is fewer.
- Chemical stability problems for API and excipient would be avoided.
- Provides stability against the effect of aging which affects the dissolution rates.

Disadvantages:**Excipients Related:**

- Problems in the uniform distribution of low dose drugs. High dose drugs having high bulk volume, poor compressibility and poor flow ability are not suitable for direct compression for example, Aluminium Hydroxide, Magnesium Hydroxide.
- The choice of excipients for direct compression is extremely critical. Direct compression diluents and binders must possess both good compressibility and good flow ability.
- Many active ingredients are not compressible either in crystalline or amorphous forms.
- Direct compression blends may lead to un blending because of difference in particle size or density of drug and excipients. Similarly, the lack of moisture may give rise to static charges, which may lead to un blending.
- Non-uniform distribution of colour, especially in tablets of deep colours.

MATERIALS:

Clobazam-Hetero Drugs Limited, Fenugreek Gum-Signet Chemical Corp., Mumbai, Karaya Gum-Signet Chemical Corp., Mumbai, Crospovidone-Signet Chemical Corp., Mumbai, Aspartame-Signet Chemical Corp., Mumbai, MCC-Aurobindo Pharma Ltd., Hyd, Talc-S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd, Magnesium stearate-S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd.

METHODOLOGY:**Pre formulation studies:****Solubility:**

Solubility of Clobazam was determined in pH 1.2, pH 7.4, pH 4.5 and 6.8 phosphate buffers. Solubility studies were performed by taking excess amount of Clobazam in beakers containing the solvents. The mixtures were shaken for 24hrs at regular intervals. The solutions were filtered by using Whatman's filter paper grade no.41. The filtered solutions are analysed by spectrophotometrically.

DRUG-EXCIPIENT COMPATIBILITY STUDIES BY I.R.:

Excipients are integral components of almost all pharmaceutical dosage forms. The successful formulation of a stable and effective solid dosage form depends on the careful selection of the excipients, which are added to facilitate administration, promote the consistent release and bioavailability of the drug and protect it from degradation.

Schematic representation of compatibility studies:

Infra-Red spectroscopy is one of the most powerful analytical techniques to identify functional groups of a drug.

Method: - The pure drug and its formulation were subjected to IR studies. In the present study, the potassium bromide disc (pellet) method was employed.

Determination of λ_{max} :

From stock solution (SS-II), 1 ml was withdrawn and the volume was made up to 10 ml with 0.1NHCL to get a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. UV scan range was taken between the wavelengths 200-400 nm.

Calibration Curve for Clobazam In 6.8pH Buffer Procedure:**Preparation of Standard Stock Solution:**

10 mg of Clobazam was accurately weighed into 10 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in small quantity of 6.8 pH phosphate Buffer. The volume was made up to 10 ml with the 6.8 pH phosphate Buffer to get a concentration of (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) standard stock-I. From this, 1 ml was withdrawn and diluted to 10 ml with distilled water to get a concentration of (100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) SS-II.

Calibration Curve in 6.8pH phosphate Buffer:

From the standard stock solution (standard stock-II), 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1 and 1.2 ml were withdrawn and volume was made up to 10 ml with 6.8 pH phosphate Buffer to give a concentration of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Absorbance of these solutions was measured against a blank of 6.8 pH phosphate Buffer at 232 nm for Clobazam and the absorbance values are summarized in Table. Calibration curve was plotted, drug concentrations versus absorbance was given in the Figure.

Formulation of oral disintegrating tablets of clobazam:

Oral disintegrating tablets of Clobazam were prepared by wet granulation technique according to the formulae given in the table. All the ingredients were weighed as per weighing record. Clobazam, MCC pH 101, and povidone were sifted together through mesh#30.

Preparation of binder solution:

Weighed quantity of purified water was dispensed in a stainless steel container and kept aside.

Dry mixing:

Clobazam, MCC pH 101 and povidone were transferred into rapid mixer granulator and mixed for 10minutes with impeller at slow speed(100rpm) and chopper off.

Granulation:

The binder solution was added to the above mixture and mixed for 2minutes with impeller at slow speed(70rpm) and chopper at high speed(100rpm). Purified water was added to the dry mix blend for 2minutes with impeller at slow speed(70rpm) and chopper at high speed(100rpm).The wet mass was kneaded for 1minute with impeller at slow speed(100rpm) and chopper at high speed(200rpm).The kneaded mass was milled using cone mill through 8mm screen at 15HZ speed.

Drying:

The wet mass was dried using hot air oven by maintaining 60^oc for 1hour 45minutes.

Sifting & milling:

The dried granules were sifted through mesh#24. particles retain on the sieve were further milled using multi mill through 1.5mm screen at 100rpm with knives in forward direction.

Milled granules were sifted through mesh #24.

Sifting of extra granular materials:

Super disintegrants were sifted through #40. Magnesium stearate was sifted through mesh #60.finally the granules were transferred into 5litre double cone blender and blended for 5minutes at 20rpm.Then the granules were compressed using tablet punching machine. The formulated tablets were evaluated for post compression parameters.

Table: 1 Formulation

Ingredients (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Clobazam	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
MCC pH 101	61	56	51	46	61	56	51	46	61	56	51	46
Povidone K30	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Fenugreek Gum	5	10	15	20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Karaya Gum	-	-	-	-	5	10	15	20	-	-	-	-
Crospovidone	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	10	15	20
Aspartame	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Talc	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Magnesium stearate	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Purified water	Q.S											
Total(mg)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Solubility studies:**

Solubility of Clobazam was carried out at 25^oC using 6.8 phosphate buffer, 7.4pH buffer ,4.5 pH acetate buffer and 0.1N HCL.

Table: 2 Solubility Studies in Different Medium

MEDIUM	SOLUBILITY (mg/ml)
0.1N HCl	0.516
6.8 pH phosphate buffer	0.755
4.5 pH Acetate buffer	0.310
7.4pH phosphate buffer	0.358

Discussion: From the above conducted solubility studies in various buffers, we can say 6.8 pH Buffer has more solubility when compared to other buffer solutions.

Drug excipient compatibility:

Drug and excipient compatibility was confirmed by comparing spectra of FT-IR analysis of pure drug with that of various excipients used in the formulation.

Figure: 1 IR spectrum of Clobazam.

Figure: 2 IR spectrum of Clobazam & excipients

Discussion: From the drug excipient compatibility studies we observe that there are no interactions between the pure drug (Clobazam) and optimized formulation (Clobazam + excipients) which indicates there are no physical changes.

Determination of λ_{\max} : -

Figure: 3 UV Spectrum curve of Clobazam

Discussion: The λ_{\max} of Clobazam solution concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ by using 6.8 pH Phosphate buffer was found to be 232 nm.

Table: 3 Calibration Curve of Clobazam in 6.8pH Buffer

Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.172
4	0.326
6	0.486
8	0.635
10	0.786
12	0.939

Figure: 4 Standard graph of Clobazam

Discussion: The linearity was found to be in the range of 2-12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in pH 6.8 buffer. The regression value was closer to 1 indicating the method obeyed Beer-lamberts' law.

Characterization of blend

Table: 4 Pre Compression parameters

Formulation Code	Derived properties		Flow properties		
	Bulk density (g/cc)	Tapped density (g/cc)	Angle of repose ($^\circ$)	Carr's index (g/cc)	Hausner's ratio (g/cc)
F1	0.446 \pm 0.002	0.529 \pm 0.005	28.24 \pm 0.21	19.48 \pm 1.12	1.18 \pm 0.008
F2	0.459 \pm 0.004	0.534 \pm 0.004	27.26 \pm 0.18	18.52 \pm 1.36	1.17 \pm 0.003
F3	0.468 \pm 0.009	0.548 \pm 0.008	25.85 \pm 0.36	15.47 \pm 2.48	1.15 \pm 0.004
F4	0.475 \pm 0.002	0.556 \pm 0.005	24.42 \pm 0.45	14.26 \pm 1.68	1.13 \pm 0.005
F5	0.459 \pm 0.008	0.537 \pm 0.008	29.26 \pm 0.19	18.95 \pm 1.96	1.17 \pm 0.004
F6	0.468 \pm 0.006	0.549 \pm 0.006	28.95 \pm 0.34	17.47 \pm 1.56	1.16 \pm 0.006
F7	0.472 \pm 0.008	0.558 \pm 0.005	27.28 \pm 0.15	15.25 \pm 1.26	1.15 \pm 0.001
F8	0.485 \pm 0.007	0.565 \pm 0.007	26.45 \pm 0.28	13.61 \pm 1.32	1.13 \pm 0.006
F9	0.468 \pm 0.006	0.542 \pm 0.005	26.26 \pm 0.14	15.25 \pm 2.62	1.14 \pm 0.003
F10	0.479 \pm 0.005	0.557 \pm 0.008	25.69 \pm 0.16	14.48 \pm 1.12	1.13 \pm 0.004
F11	0.485 \pm 0.008	0.568 \pm 0.007	24.35 \pm 0.34	13.36 \pm 1.32	1.12 \pm 0.005
F12	0.496 \pm 0.014	0.579 \pm 0.006	23.45 \pm 0.42	11.42 \pm 0.97	1.09 \pm 0.003

Discussion:

The angle of repose of different formulations was $\leq 29.26 \pm 0.19$, which indicates that material had good flow property. So, it was confirmed that the flow property of blends was free flowing. The bulk density of blend was found between $0.446 \pm 0.002 \text{ g/cm}^3$ to $0.496 \pm 0.014 \text{ g/cm}^3$. Tapped density was found between $0.529 \pm 0.005 \text{ g/cm}^3$ to $0.579 \pm 0.006 \text{ g/cm}^3$. These values indicate that the blends had good flow property. Carr's index for all the formulations was found to be between 11.42 ± 0.97 - 19.48 ± 1.12 and Hausner's ratio from 1.09 ± 0.003 - 1.18 ± 0.008 which reveals that the blends have good flow character.

Characterization of tablets:**Post Compression parameters:**

All the batches of tablet formulations were characterized for official evaluation parameters like Weight variation, Hardness, Friability, Tablet thickness and drug content and results are shown in the table.

Table: 5 Characterization Clobazam oral disintegrating tablets

Formulation	Average Weight (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Disintegrating time(sec)
F1	400.2±0.09	4.1±0.08	5.1±0.05	0.79±0.02	25.28±0.02
F2	401.3±0.08	4.2±0.06	5.5±0.06	0.63±0.06	23.47±0.05
F3	402.4±0.05	4.4±0.08	5.9±0.07	0.53±0.08	19.36±0.06
F4	399.6±0.08	4.6±0.04	5.2±0.09	0.65±0.02	16.18±0.08
F5	403.2±0.06	4.5±0.03	5.6±0.06	0.59±0.08	22.28±0.02
F6	398.8±0.08	4.4±0.09	5.7±0.04	0.48±0.06	20.19±0.07
F7	400.3±0.07	4.3±0.08	5.5±0.08	0.64±0.04	18.44±0.09
F8	402.6±0.05	4.4±0.09	5.2±0.05	0.69±0.08	15.14±0.02
F9	401.2±0.04	4.6±0.05	5.5±0.06	0.55±0.02	18.19±0.06
F10	403.3±0.08	4.2±0.08	5.3±0.08	0.62±0.46	17.16±0.02
F11	402.2±0.08	4.1±0.06	5.9±0.06	0.59±0.32	15.18±0.12
F12	400.1±0.05	4.7±0.09	6.1±0.09	0.43±0.58	11.27±0.04

Discussion:

Hardness of the tablet was acceptable and uniform from batch to batch variation, which was found to be 5.1 ± 0.05 – $6.1 \pm 0.09 \text{ kg/cm}^2$. All the formulations passed the weight variation test as the % weight variation was within the pharmacopoeial limits of the tablet weight. Friability values were found to be less than 1% in all the formulations F1 – F12 and considered to be satisfactory ensuring that all the formulations are mechanically stable. Disintegration time as per IP, for all the formulations the optimized formulation F12 was disintegrated within 11.27 ± 0.04 seconds, which was well within IP limit. Formulations with Crospovidone as super disintegrants shows quicker disintegration among all the formulations. Crospovidone with 25 mg concentration as a super disintegrant shows very less disintegration time.

Drug content uniformity of formulations:

The prepared formulations were analyzed for drug content and the data is reported in below Table. The drug content was found to be within the limits which show that the drug was uniformly distributed in all the formulations.

Table: 6 Drug content uniformity of formulations F1-F12:

Tablet formulation	% of drug content
F1	87.14 %
F2	89.25%
F3	91.36%
F4	94.42%
F5	88.28%
F6	91.42%
F7	93.29%
F8	96.42%
F9	93.26%
F10	94.48%
F11	96.25%
F12	98.38%

Discussion: % drug content values of formulation F1 –F12 was found to be in the range of 87.14%-98.38%.

Dissolution studies:

The prepared tablets were subjected to dissolution studies in order to know the amount drug release. As the concentration of super disintegrant increased, the drug release time decreased.

Table: 7 Percentage Cumulative drug release of formulations F1-F12

Time (Min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	39.24 %	43.85 %	46.17 %	45.45 %	37.41 %	39.05 %	43.61 %	49.64 %	36.14 %	46.25 %	58.21 %	62.48 %
15	48.78 %	58.75 %	53.31 %	57.05 %	43.61 %	45.38 %	52.42 %	56.42 %	48.38 %	52.26 %	62.81 %	69.25 %
20	59.21 %	67.61 %	61.46 %	69.49 %	51.36 %	53.42 %	64.63 %	78.71 %	57.85 %	59.48 %	69.98 %	75.84 %
25	68.65 %	75.34 %	74.82 %	75.42 %	64.54 %	67.28 %	72.45 %	81.43 %	64.23 %	65.25 %	78.85 %	86.47 %
30	76.24 %	81.46 %	87.74 %	84.24 %	72.44 %	71.42 %	85.45 %	88.44 %	78.53 %	78.64 %	85.25 %	93.48 %
45	86.89 %	88.14 %	93.53 %	96.98 %	79.18 %	80.28 %	94.85 %	97.44 %	82.74 %	86.25 %	96.46 %	99.72 %
60	97.42 %	96.49 %			83.25 %	88.26 %			91.85 %	93.48 %		

Discussion:

From the invitro drug release studies it was observed that the formulations containing Fenugreek Gum (F1-F4) as natural super disintegrant in the concentrations of (5,10, 15 and 20mg). F1, F2, shows 97.42% and 96.49% drug release at the end of 60minutes. Whereas F3 and F4 shows 93.53% and 96.98% drug release at the end of 45 minutes.

From the invitro drug release studies it was observed that the formulations containing Karaya Gum (F5-F8) as natural super disintegrant in the concentrations of (5,10, 15 and 20mg). F5, F6, shows 83.25% and 88.26% drug release at the end of 60minutes. Whereas F7 and F8 shows 93.53% and 96.98% drug release at the end of 45 minutes.

From the invitro drug release studies it was observed that the formulations containing Crospovidone (F9-F12) as natural super disintegrant in the concentrations of (5,10, 15 and 20mg). F9, F10, shows 91.85% and 93.48% drug

release at the end of 60 minutes. Whereas F11 and F12 shows 96.46% and **99.72%** drug release at the end of 45 minutes.

By comparing the dissolutions profiles of formulations F1-F12 containing super disintegrants in the concentrations of (5,10, 15 and 20mg), the drug release was increased when the polymer concentration increased. Among all the formulations F12 containing 20mg of Crospovidone shows 99.72% drug release at the end of 60min. So F12 formulation was considered as the optimized formulation. Further kinetics were measured for F12 formulation.

Drug Release Kinetics Studies:

Zero Order Release Kinetics

Figure: 5 Zero Order Plot Of Clobazam F12 Formulation

First Order Release Kinetics

Figure: 6 First Order Plot Of Clobazam F12 Formulation (Time Vs Log% Ara)

Table: 8 Order of Kinetic Values of Formulation F12

Order of kinetics	Zero order	First order
Regression values	0.708	0.885

Discussion:

The drug release from the oral disintegrating tablets was explained by the using mathematical model equations such as zero order, first order methods. Based on the regression values it was concluded that the optimized formulation F12 follows First order drug release.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSION:

- The present study is an attempt to select the best possible diluent - disintegrant combination to formulate Immediate release tablets of Clobazam, which disintegrates in matter of seconds in the oral cavity, thereby reducing the time of onset of pharmacological action.
- Fenugreek Gum, Karaya Gum and Crospovidone, were used as disintegrants. In all the formulations, Magnesium stearate were used as lubricant respectively.
- The results of the drug – excipient compatibility studies revealed that there was no chemical interaction between the pure drug and excipients.
- Intra and extra granulation technique was employed to formulate the tablets, because of its cost effectiveness and due to reduced number of manufacturing steps.
- The precompression parameters like bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index and angle of repose were determined. All the formulations showed acceptable flow properties.
- The post compression parameters like the hardness, thickness, friability and weight variation, disintegration time, disintegration time in oral cavity and Invitro release were carried out and the values were found to be within IP limits.
- The percentage drug content of all the tablets was found to be between 87.14%-98.38% of Clobazam, which was within the acceptable limits.
- Among all the formulations **F12** shows 99.72% drug release at the end of 60min. F12 contains Crosspovidone (12.5mg), it shows better % drug release when compared to other formulations.
- So F12 was considered as the optimized formulation.

- The drug release kinetics shows that the optimized formulation F12 follows First order drug release.

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